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New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer's Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph

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1 ABSTRACT

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a Vertex-Cut pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the following expression is called Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$; Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperVertex-Cut). Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called an Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic

v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; an Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; an Extreme V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; a Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; an Extreme V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the

Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient. In this scientific research, new setting is introduced for new SuperHyperNotions, namely, a SuperHyperVertex-Cut and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Two different types of SuperHyperDefinitions are debut for them but the research goes further and the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass based on that are well-defined and well-reviewed. The literature review is implemented in the whole of this research. For shining the elegancy and the significancy of this research, the comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are featured. The definitions are followed by the examples and the instances thus the clarifications are driven with different tools. The applications are figured out to make sense about the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. The “Cancer’s Recognition” are the under research to figure out the challenges make sense about ongoing and upcoming research. The special case is up. The cells are viewed in the deemed ways. There are different types of them. Some of them are individuals and some of them are well-modeled by the group of cells. These types are all officially called “SuperHyperVertex” but the relations amid them all officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. The frameworks “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” are chosen and elected to research about “Cancer’s Recognition”. Thus these complex and dense SuperHyperModels open up some avenues to research on theoretical segments and “Cancer’s Recognition”. Some avenues are posed to pursue this research. It’s also officially collected in the form of some questions and some problems. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Assume a SuperHyperGraph. Then δ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut is a maximal of SuperHyperVertices with a maximum cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the (Neutrosophic) cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$: there are $|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is an δ -SuperHyperDefensive; a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut is a maximal Neutrosophic of SuperHyperVertices with maximum Neutrosophic cardinality such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$ there are: $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$; and $|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta$. The first Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive. And the second Expression, holds if S is a Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive. It’s useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Since there’s more ways to get type-results to make a SuperHyperVertex-Cut more understandable. For the sake of having Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, there’s a need to “redefine” the notion of a “SuperHyperVertex-Cut”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there’s the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. It’s redefined a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut if the mentioned Table holds, concerning, “The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with the key points, “The Values of The Vertices & The Number of Position in Alphabet”, “The Values of The SuperVertices&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The Edges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The HyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Vertices”, “The Values of The SuperHyperEdges&The maximum Values of Its Endpoints”. To get structural examples and instances, I’m

going to introduce the next SuperHyperClass of SuperHyperGraph based on a SuperHyperVertex-Cut . It's the main. It'll be disciplinary to have the foundation of previous definition in the kind of SuperHyperClass. If there's a need to have all SuperHyperVertex-Cut until the SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then it's officially called a "SuperHyperVertex-Cut" but otherwise, it isn't a SuperHyperVertex-Cut . There are some instances about the clarifications for the main definition titled a "SuperHyperVertex-Cut ". These two examples get more scrutiny and discernment since there are characterized in the disciplinary ways of the SuperHyperClass based on a SuperHyperVertex-Cut . For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut" and a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut ". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's redefined "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" if the intended Table holds. And a SuperHyperVertex-Cut are redefined to a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut" if the intended Table holds. It's useful to define "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut more understandable. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses if the intended Table holds. Thus SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are "Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite", "Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite", and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel" if the intended Table holds. A SuperHyperGraph has a "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut" where it's the strongest [the maximum Neutrosophic value from all the SuperHyperVertex-Cut amid the maximum value amid all SuperHyperVertices from a SuperHyperVertex-Cut .] SuperHyperVertex-Cut . A graph is a SuperHyperUniform if it's a SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows. It's SuperHyperPath if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions; it's SuperHyperVertex-Cut if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperStar it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges; it's SuperHyperBipartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's SuperHyperMultiPartite it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common; it's a SuperHyperWheel if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex. The SuperHyperModel proposes the specific designs and the specific architectures. The SuperHyperModel is officially called "SuperHyperGraph" and "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". In this SuperHyperModel, The "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperVertices" and the common and intended properties between "specific" cells and "specific group" of cells are SuperHyperModeled as "SuperHyperEdges". Sometimes, it's useful to have some degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy, and neutrality to have more precise SuperHyperModel which in this case the SuperHyperModel is called "Neutrosophic". In the future research, the foundation will be based on the "Cancer's Recognition" and the results and the definitions will be introduced in redeemed ways. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it's called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is

identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut or the strongest SuperHyperVertex-Cut in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. For the longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut, called SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and the strongest SuperHyperVertex-Cut, called Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges but it's not enough since it's essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. There isn't any formation of any SuperHyperVertex-Cut but literarily, it's the deformation of any SuperHyperVertex-Cut. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn't form. A basic familiarity with Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut theory, SuperHyperGraphs, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs theory are proposed.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Cancer's Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are some ideas in the featured frameworks of motivations. I try to bring the motivations in the narrative ways. Some cells have been faced with some attacks from the situation which is caused by the cancer's attacks. In this case, there are some embedded analysis on the ongoing situations which in that, the cells could be labelled as some groups and some groups or individuals have excessive labels which all are raised from the behaviors to overcome the cancer's attacks. In the embedded situations, the individuals of cells and the groups of cells could be considered as "new groups". Thus it motivates us to find the proper SuperHyperModels for getting more proper analysis on this messy story. I've found the SuperHyperModels which are officially called "SuperHyperGraphs" and "Extreme SuperHyperGraphs". In this SuperHyperModel, the cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperVertices" and the relations between the individuals of cells and the groups of cells are defined as "SuperHyperEdges". Thus it's another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on the "Cancer's Recognition". Sometimes, the situations get worst. The situation is passed from the certainty and precise style. Thus it's the beyond them. There are three descriptions, namely, the degrees of determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality, for any object based on vague forms, namely, incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The latter model could be considered on the previous SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperModel. It's SuperHyperGraph but it's officially called "Extreme SuperHyperGraphs". The cancer is the disease but the model is going to figure out what's going on this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The recognition of the cancer could help to find some treatments for

this disease. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognition” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the forms of alliances’ styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperVertex-Cut” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. The recognition of the cancer in the long-term function. The specific region has been assigned by the model [it’s called SuperHyperGraph] and the long cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn’t be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it’s said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what’s happened and what’s done. There are some specific models, which are well-known and they’ve got the names, and some general models. The moves and the traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by an Extreme SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the optimal SuperHyperVertex-Cut or the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in those Extreme SuperHyperModels. Some general results are introduced. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Extreme SuperHyperPath s have only two SuperHyperEdges but it’s not enough since it’s essential to have at least three SuperHyperEdges to form any style of a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. There isn’t any formation of any SuperHyperVertex-Cut but literarily, it’s the deformation of any SuperHyperVertex-Cut. It, literarily, deforms and it doesn’t form.

Question 2.1. *How to define the SuperHyperNotions and to do research on them to find the “ amount of SuperHyperVertex-Cut” of either individual of cells or the groups of cells based on the fixed cell or the fixed group of cells, extensively, the “amount of SuperHyperVertex-Cut” based on the fixed groups of cells or the fixed groups of group of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for the “Cancer’s Recognition” in terms of these messy and dense SuperHyperModels where embedded notions are illustrated?*

It’s motivation to find notions to use in this dense model is titled “SuperHyperGraphs”. Thus it motivates us to define different types of “ SuperHyperVertex-Cut” and “Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut” on “SuperHyperGraph” and “Extreme SuperHyperGraph”. Then the research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and to find some connections amid this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to get some instances and examples to make clarifications about the framework of this research. The general results and some results about some connections are some avenues to make key point of this research, “Cancer’s Recognition”, more understandable and more clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. In the beginning, I introduce basic definitions to clarify about preliminaries. In the subsection “Preliminaries”, initial definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are deeply-introduced and in-depth-discussed. The elementary concepts are clarified and illustrated completely and sometimes review literature are applied to make sense about what’s going to figure out about the upcoming sections. The main definitions and their clarifications alongside some results about new notions, SuperHyperVertex-Cut and Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, are figured out in sections “ SuperHyperVertex-Cut”

and “Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut”. In the sense of tackling on getting results and in Vertex-Cut to make sense about continuing the research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Extreme SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, corresponded SuperHyperClasses are figured out to debut what’s done in this section, titled “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. As going back to origin of the notions, there are some smart steps toward the common notions to extend the new notions in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph, in the sections “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. The starter research about the general SuperHyperRelations and as concluding and closing section of theoretical research are contained in the section “General Results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and they are well-known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions as elicited and discussed in the sections, “General Results”, “SuperHyperVertex-Cut”, “Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what’s done about the SuperHyperNotions to make sense about excellency of this research and going to figure out the word “best” as the description and adjective for this research as presented in section, “SuperHyperVertex-Cut”. The keyword of this research debut in the section “Applications in Cancer’s Recognition” with two cases and subsections “Case 1: The Initial Steps Toward SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: The Increasing Steps Toward SuperHyperMultipartite as SuperHyperModel”. In the section, “Open Problems”, there are some scrutiny and discernment on what’s done and what’s happened in this research in the terms of “questions” and “problems” to make sense to figure out this research in featured style. The advantages and the limitations of this research alongside about what’s done in this research to make sense and to get sense about what’s figured out are included in the section, “Conclusion and Closing Remarks”.

3 Extreme Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [134],Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [134],Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [134],Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [134],Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](Ref. [134], Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [134],Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (Ref. [134],Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (Ref. [134],Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to Ref. [134].

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [134],Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Vertex-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a

falsity-membership function of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [134], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a Vertex-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [134], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'}), T''_V(E_{i'})$, and $T'''_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.6 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [134], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG).

Definition 3.7 (t-norm). (Ref. [134], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$;
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

Definition 3.8. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

and $F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$

Definition 3.9. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.10. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.11 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [134], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.12. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.13. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Definition 3.14. Let a pair $S = (V, E)$ be a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S . Then a sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;

- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$; 464
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that 465
 $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$. 466

Definition 3.15. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 467

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items. 468

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**; 469
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}$, $|E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's V_i , $|V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**; 470
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**; 471
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}$, $|V_i| \geq 1$, $|E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** . 472
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Definition 3.16 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). 474

(Ref. [134], Definition 5.3, p.7). 475

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have 476

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$; 477
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$; 478
- (iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$; 479
- (iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$. 480

Definition 3.17 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [134], Definition 5.4, p.7). 481
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Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 483
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- (ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 485
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- (x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 488
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- (xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 491
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- (xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

Definition 3.18. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria** holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

- (ii) **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria** holds

$$\forall E_i \in E' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

$$\text{and } |E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (iii) **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria** holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

- (iv) **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the following expression is called **Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut criteria** holds

$$\forall V_i \in V' : S = (V, E) \text{ is disconnect-able;}$$

$$\text{and } |V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}};$$

- (v) **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Definition 3.19. ((Neutrosophic) SuperHyperVertex-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum

- Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 531-534
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 535-544
- (iv) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient; 545-555
- (v) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 556-563
- (vi) a **Neutrosophic V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 564-571
- (vii) an **Extreme V-SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 572-580

Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Neutrosophic e-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic re-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Neutrosophic v-SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and Neutrosophic rv-SuperHyperVertex-Cut and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Neutrosophic coefficients defined as the Neutrosophic number of the maximum Neutrosophic cardinality of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet S of high Neutrosophic cardinality conseNeighborive Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges and Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut; and the Neutrosophic power is corresponded to its Neutrosophic coefficient.

Definition 3.20. ((Extreme/Neutrosophic) δ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then

- (i) an δ -**SuperHyperVertex-Cut** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut such that either of the following expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)| > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)| < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))| + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is an δ -**SuperHyperDefensive**;

- (ii) a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut** is a Neutrosophic kind of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut such that either of the following Neutrosophic expressions hold for the Neutrosophic cardinalities of SuperHyperNeighbors of $s \in S$:

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} > |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta;$$

$$|S \cap N(s)|_{Neutrosophic} < |S \cap (V \setminus N(s))|_{Neutrosophic} + \delta.$$

The Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperOffensive**. And the Expression (3.1), holds if S is a **Neutrosophic δ -SuperHyperDefensive**.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.21. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Definition 3.22. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.22)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.23. Assume a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex-Cut** if the Table (3) holds.

4 Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 4.1. (Extreme event).

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.23)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Any Extreme k -subset of A of V is called **Extreme k -event** and if $k = 2$, then Extreme subset of A of V is called **Extreme event**. The following expression is called **Extreme probability** of A .

$$E(A) = \sum_{a \in A} E(a). \quad (4.1)$$

Definition 4.2. (Extreme Independent).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. s Extreme k -events $A_i, i \in I$ is called **Extreme s -independent** if the following expression is called **Extreme s -independent criteria**

$$E(\cap_{i \in I} A_i) = \prod_{i \in I} P(A_i).$$

And if $s = 2$, then Extreme k -events of A and B is called **Extreme independent**. The following expression is called **Extreme independent criteria**

$$E(A \cap B) = P(A)P(B). \quad (4.2)$$

Definition 4.3. (Extreme Variable).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Any k -function Vertex-Cut like E is called **Extreme k -Variable**. If $k = 2$, then any 2-function Vertex-Cut like E is called **Extreme Variable**.

The notion of independent on Extreme Variable is likewise.

Definition 4.4. (Extreme Expectation).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. an Extreme k -Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Expectation** if the following expression is called **Extreme Expectation criteria**

$$Ex(E) = \sum_{\alpha \in V} E(\alpha)P(\alpha).$$

Definition 4.5. (Extreme Crossing).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. an Extreme number is called **Extreme Crossing** if the following expression is called **Extreme Crossing criteria**

$$Cr(S) = \min\{\text{Number of Crossing in a Plane Embedding of } S\}.$$

Lemma 4.6. *Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let m and n propose special Vertex-Cut. Then with $m \geq 4n$,*

Proof. Consider a planar embedding G of G with $cr(G)$ crossings. Let S be an Extreme random k -subset of V obtained by choosing each SuperHyperVertex of G Extreme independently with probability Vertex-Cut $p := 4n/m$, and set $H := G[S]$ and $H := G[S]$.

Define random variables X, Y, Z on V as follows: X is the Extreme number of SuperHyperVertices, Y the Extreme number of SuperHyperEdges, and Z the Extreme

number of crossings of H . The trivial bound noted above, when applied to H , yields the inequality $Z \geq cr(H) \geq Y - 3X$. By linearity of Extreme Expectation,

$$E(Z) \geq E(Y) - 3E(X).$$

Now $E(X) = pn$, $E(Y) = p^2m$ (each SuperHyperEdge having some SuperHyperEnds) and $E(Z) = p^4cr(G)$ (each crossing being defined by some SuperHyperVertices). Hence

$$p^4cr(G) \geq p^2m - 3pn.$$

Dividing both sides by p^4 , we have:

$$cr(G) \geq \frac{pm - 3n}{p^3} = \frac{n}{(4n/m)^3} = \frac{1}{64}m^3n^2.$$

□ 673

Theorem 4.7. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let l be the Extreme number of SuperHyperLines in the plane passing through at least $k + 1$ of these points, where $1 \leq k \leq 2\sqrt{2n}$. Then $l < 32n^2/k^3$.

Proof. Form an Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdge are the segments between conseNeighborive points on the SuperHyperLines which pass through at least $k + 1$ points of P . This Extreme SuperHyperGraph has at least kl SuperHyperEdges and Extreme crossing at most l choose two. Thus either $kl < 4n$, in which case $l < 4n/k \leq 32n^2/k^3$, or $l^2/2 > 1$ choose $2 \geq cr(G) \geq (kl)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and again $l < 32n^2/k^3$. □

Theorem 4.8. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let P be a SuperHyperSet of n points in the plane, and let k be the number of pairs of points of P at unit SuperHyperDistance. Then $k < 5n^{4/3}$.

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Draw a SuperHyperUnit SuperHyperCircle around each SuperHyperPoint of P . Let n_i be the Extreme number of these SuperHyperCircles passing through exactly i points of P . Then $\sum i = 0^{n-1}n_i = n$ and $k = \frac{1}{2} \sum i = 0^{n-1}in_i$. Now form an Extreme SuperHyperGraph H with SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet P whose SuperHyperEdges are the SuperHyperArcs between conseNeighborive SuperHyperPoints on the SuperHyperCircles that pass through at least three SuperHyperPoints of P . Then

$$e(H) = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} in_i = 2k - n_1 - 2n_2 \geq 2k - 2n.$$

Some SuperHyperPairs of SuperHyperVertices of H might be joined by some parallel SuperHyperEdges. Delete from H one of each SuperHyperPair of parallel SuperHyperEdges, so as to obtain a simple Extreme SuperHyperGraph G with $e(G) \geq k - n$. Now $cr(G) \leq n(n - 1)$ because G is formed from at most n SuperHyperCircles, and any two SuperHyperCircles cross at most twice. Thus either $e(G) < 4n$, in which case $k < 5n < 5n^{4/3}$, or $n^2 > n(n - 1) \geq cr(G) \geq (k - n)^3/64n^2$ by the Extreme Crossing Lemma, and $k < 4n^{4/3} + n < 5n^{4/3}$. □

Proposition 4.9. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X be a nonnegative Extreme Variable and t a positive real number. Then

$$P(X \geq t) \leq \frac{E(X)}{t}.$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} E(X) &= \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V\} \geq \sum \{X(a)P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= \sum \{tP(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} = t \sum \{P(a) : a \in V, X(a) \geq t\} \\ &= tP(X \geq t). \end{aligned}$$

Dividing the first and last members by t yields the asserted inequality. $\square$

Corollary 4.10. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X_n be a nonnegative integer-valued variable in a probability Vertex-Cut $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $E(X_n) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, then $P(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Proof.

Theorem 4.11. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most $\lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$.

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. A special SuperHyperGraph in $G_{n,p}$ is up. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ and let S be a given SuperHyperSet of $k+1$ SuperHyperVertices of G , where $k \in \mathbb{N}$. The probability that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G is $(1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}$, this being the probability that none of the $\binom{k+1}{2}$ pairs of SuperHyperVertices of S is a SuperHyperEdge of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph G .

Let A_S denote the event that S is a stable SuperHyperSet of G , and let X_S denote the indicator Extreme Variable for this Extreme Event. By equation, we have

$$E(X_S) = P(X_S = 1) = P(A_S) = (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

Let X be the number of stable SuperHyperSets of cardinality $k+1$ in G . Then

$$X = \sum \{X_S : S \subseteq V, |S| = k+1\}$$

and so, by those,

$$E(X) = \sum \{E(X_S) : S \subseteq V, |S| = k+1\} = \binom{n}{k+1} (1-p)^{\binom{k+1}{2}}.$$

We bound the right-hand side by invoking two elementary inequalities:

$$\binom{n}{k+1} \leq \frac{n^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} \text{ and } 1-p \leq e^{-p}.$$

This yields the following upper bound on $E(X)$.

$$E(X) \leq \frac{n^{k+1} e^{-p \binom{k+1}{2}}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{n e^{-pk/2k+1}}{(k+1)!}$$

Suppose now that $k = \lceil 2p^{-1} \log n \rceil$. Then $k \geq 2p^{-1} \log n$, so $n e^{-pk/2k+1} \leq 1$. Because k grows at least as fast as the logarithm of n , implies that $E(X) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Because X is integer-valued and nonnegative, we deduce from Corollary that $P(X = 0) \rightarrow 1$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Consequently, an Extreme SuperHyperGraph in $\mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has stability number at most k . $\square$

Definition 4.12. (Extreme Variance). 733

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. an Extreme k-Variable E has a number is called **Extreme Variance** if the following expression is called **Extreme Variance criteria** 734
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$$Vx(E) = Ex((X - Ex(X))^2).$$

Theorem 4.13. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X be an Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then 737
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$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) \leq \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X be an Extreme Variable and let t be a positive real number. Then 740
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$$E(|X - Ex(X)| \geq t) = E((X - Ex(X))^2 \geq t^2) \leq \frac{Ex((X - Ex(X))^2)}{t^2} = \frac{V(X)}{t^2}.$$

□ 743

Corollary 4.14. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let X_n be an Extreme Variable in a probability Vertex-Cut $(V_n, E_n), n \geq 1$. If $Ex(X_n) \neq 0$ and $V(X_n) \ll E^2(X_n)$, then 744
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$$E(X_n = 0) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Set $X := X_n$ and $t := |Ex(X_n)|$ in Chebyshev's Inequality, and observe that $E(X_n = 0) \leq E(|X_n - Ex(X_n)| \geq |Ex(X_n)|)$ because $|X_n - Ex(X_n)| = |Ex(X_n)|$ when $X_n = 0$. 748
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Theorem 4.15. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$. For $0 \leq k \leq n$, set $f(k) := (n \text{ choose } k)2^{-(k \text{ choose } 2)}$ and let k^* be the least value of k for which $f(k)$ is less than one. Then almost surely $\alpha(G)$ takes one of the three values $k^* - 2, k^* - 1, k^*$. 752
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Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. As in the proof of related Theorem, the result is straightforward. 756
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Corollary 4.16. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,1/2}$ and let f and k^* be as defined in previous Theorem. Then either: 759
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(i). $f(k^*) \ll 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 2$ or $k^* - 1$, 762
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or

(ii). $f(k^* - 1) \gg 1$, in which case almost surely $\alpha(G)$ is equal to either $k^* - 1$ or k^* . 764

Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. 765
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Definition 4.17. (Extreme Threshold). 767

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let P be a monotone property of SuperHyperGraphs (one which is preserved when SuperHyperEdges are added). Then a **Extreme Threshold** for P is a function $f(n)$ such that: 768
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(i). if $p \ll f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely does not have P , 772

(ii). if $p \gg f(n)$, then $G \in \mathcal{G}_{n,p}$ almost surely has P . 773

Definition 4.18. (Extreme Balanced). 774

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let F be a fixed Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then there is a threshold function for the property of containing a copy of F as an Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph is called **Extreme Balanced**. 775
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Theorem 4.19. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. Let F be a nonempty balanced Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph with k SuperHyperVertices and l SuperHyperEdges. Then $n^{-k/l}$ is a threshold function for the property of containing F as an Extreme SubSuperHyperGraph. 779
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Proof. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider $S = (V, E)$ is a probability Vertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 784
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Example 4.20. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 786
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- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 788
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}}$$

$$= \{\}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}}$$

$$= \{\}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 0z^0.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme 796
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Figure 1. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 2. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 3. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 4. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_1\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_3\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_5\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely

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Figure 5. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 6. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 7. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 8. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
 & \{E_4\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 & = z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} & \\
 & = \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 & = 3z.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} & \\
 & = \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 & = 0z^0. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} & \\
 & = \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} & \\
 & = 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

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Figure 9. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

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- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^6. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 6z^2. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 10. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 11. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 12. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 13. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{V_5\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 14. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 15. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 5z^2. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_5\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 5z^2. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{V_5\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^5.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 16. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 17. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 18. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 868
869
870

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_1, E_2, E_3, E_4, E_5\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 5z^2. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 871
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 19. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{V_1\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \{E_2\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{10}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 20. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= z^9 + z^{12}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proposition 4.21. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Proposition 4.22. Assume a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme

Figure 21. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

Figure 22. The Extreme SuperHyperGraphs Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.3)

SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct *Extreme SuperHyperVertices* in an *Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut*, minus all *Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor* to some of them but not all of them. 899
900
901

Proposition 4.23. Assume a connected *Extreme SuperHyperGraph* $ESHG : (V, E)$. If an *Extreme SuperHyperEdge* $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z *Extreme SuperHyperVertices*, then the *Extreme cardinality* of the *Extreme R-Vertex-Cut* is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the *Extreme cardinality* of the *Extreme R-Vertex-Cut* is at least the maximum *Extreme number* of *Extreme SuperHyperVertices* of the *Extreme SuperHyperEdges* with the maximum number of the *Extreme SuperHyperEdges*. In other words, the maximum number of the *Extreme SuperHyperEdges* contains the maximum *Extreme number* of *Extreme SuperHyperVertices* are renamed to *Extreme Vertex-Cut* in some cases but the maximum number of the *Extreme SuperHyperEdge* with the maximum *Extreme number* of *Extreme SuperHyperVertices*, has the *Extreme SuperHyperVertices* are contained in an *Extreme R-Vertex-Cut*. 902
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Proposition 4.24. Assume a simple *Extreme SuperHyperGraph* $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then the *Extreme number* of *type-result-R-Vertex-Cut* has, the least *Extreme cardinality*, the lower sharp *Extreme bound* for *Extreme cardinality*, is the *Extreme cardinality* of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_{E'}, c_{E''}, c_{E'''}\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}.$$

If there's an *Extreme type-result-R-Vertex-Cut* with the least *Extreme cardinality*, the lower sharp *Extreme bound* for cardinality. 910
911

Proposition 4.25. Assume a connected loopless *Extreme SuperHyperGraph* $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally, 912
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Is an *Extreme type-result-Vertex-Cut*. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of an *Extreme type-result-Vertex-Cut* is the cardinality of 914
915

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} &= \{V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, E_3, V_4, E_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_3, V_4, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} &= z^5. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Assume a connected loopless *Extreme SuperHyperGraph* $ESHG : (V, E)$. The *SuperHyperSet* of the *SuperHyperVertices* $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ isn't a *quasi-R-Vertex-Cut* since neither amount of *Extreme SuperHyperEdges* nor amount of *SuperHyperVertices* where amount refers to the *Extreme number* of *SuperHyperVertices*(-/*SuperHyperEdges*) more than one to form any kind of *SuperHyperSet* or any number of *SuperHyperEdges*. Let us consider the *Extreme SuperHyperSet*

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E,E'=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}.$$

This *Extreme SuperHyperSet* of the *Extreme SuperHyperVertices* has the eligibilities to propose property such that there's no *Extreme SuperHyperVertex* of an *Extreme*

SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices but the maximum Extreme cardinality indicates that these Extreme type-SuperHyperSets couldn't give us the Extreme lower bound in the term of Extreme sharpness. In other words, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices implies at least on-quasi-triangle style is up but sometimes the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E' = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is free-quasi-triangle and it doesn't make a contradiction to the supposition on the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Thus the minimum case never happens in the generality of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs. Thus if we assume in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Is a quasi-R-Vertex-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of a quasi-R-Vertex-Cut is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Then we've lost some connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraphs titled free-triangle, on-triangle, and their quasi-types but the SuperHyperStable is only up in this quasi-R-Vertex-Cut. It's the contradiction to that fact on the generality. There are some counterexamples to deny this statement. One of them comes from the setting of the graph titled path and cycle as the counterexamples-classes or reversely direction star as the examples-classes, are well-known classes in that setting and they could be considered as the examples-classes and counterexamples-classes for the tight bound of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}}$$

Let $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ in mind. There's no necessity on the SuperHyperEdge since we need at least two SuperHyperVertices to form a SuperHyperEdge. It doesn't withdraw the principles of the main definition since there's no condition to be satisfied but the condition is on the existence of the SuperHyperEdge instead of acting on the SuperHyperVertices. In other words, if there's a SuperHyperEdge, then the Extreme SuperHyperSet has the necessary condition for the intended definition to be applied. Thus the $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$ is withdrawn not by the conditions of the main definition but by the necessity of the pre-condition on the usage of the main definition.

The Extreme structure of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut decorates the Extreme SuperHyperVertices don't have received any Extreme connections so as this Extreme style implies different versions of Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum Extreme cardinality in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are spotlight. The lower Extreme bound is to have the maximum Extreme groups of Extreme SuperHyperVertices have perfect Extreme connections inside each of SuperHyperEdges and the outside of this Extreme SuperHyperSet doesn't matter but regarding the connectedness of the used Extreme SuperHyperGraph arising from its Extreme properties taken from the fact that it's simple. If there's no more than one Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the targeted Extreme SuperHyperSet, then there's no Extreme

connection. Furthermore, the Extreme existence of one Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no Extreme effect to talk about the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. Since at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices involve to make a title in the Extreme background of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The Extreme SuperHyperGraph is obvious if it has no Extreme SuperHyperEdge but at least two Extreme SuperHyperVertices make the Extreme version of Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the Extreme setting of non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It's necessary to mention that the word "Simple" is used as Extreme adjective for the initial Extreme SuperHyperGraph, induces there's no Extreme appearance of the loop Extreme version of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge and this Extreme SuperHyperGraph is said to be loopless. The Extreme adjective "loop" on the basic Extreme framework engages one Extreme SuperHyperVertex but it never happens in this Extreme setting. With these Extreme bases, on an Extreme SuperHyperGraph, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge thus there's at least an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut has the Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus, an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut has the Extreme cardinality at least an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V \setminus V \setminus \{z\}$. This Extreme SuperHyperSet isn't an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut since either the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is an obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel thus it never happens since there's no Extreme usage of this Extreme framework and even more there's no Extreme connection inside or the Extreme SuperHyperGraph isn't obvious and as its consequences, there's an Extreme contradiction with the term "Extreme R-Vertex-Cut" since the maximum Extreme cardinality never happens for this Extreme style of the Extreme SuperHyperSet and beyond that there's no Extreme connection inside as mentioned in first Extreme case in the forms of drawback for this selected Extreme SuperHyperSet. Let

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Comes up. This Extreme case implies having the Extreme style of on-quasi-triangle Extreme style on the every Extreme elements of this Extreme SuperHyperSet. Precisely, the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut is the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that some Extreme amount of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are on-quasi-triangle Extreme style. The Extreme cardinality of the v SuperHypeSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, a_{E'}, b_{E'}, c_{E'}, \dots\}_{E, E'} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\}$$

Is the maximum in comparison to the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

But the lower Extreme bound is up. Thus the minimum Extreme cardinality of the maximum Extreme cardinality ends up the Extreme discussion. The first Extreme term refers to the Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph but this key point is enough since there's an Extreme SuperHyperClass of an Extreme SuperHyperGraph has no on-quasi-triangle Extreme style amid some amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices. This Extreme setting of the Extreme SuperHyperModel proposes an Extreme SuperHyperSet has only some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices from one Extreme SuperHyperEdge such that there's no Extreme amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges more than one involving these some amount of these Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The Extreme cardinality of this Extreme SuperHyperSet is the maximum and the Extreme case is occurred in the minimum Extreme situation. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)} \mid |E| = \max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V, E)}\}\} \cdot$$

Has the maximum Extreme cardinality such that

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Contains some Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct-covers-order-amount Extreme SuperHyperEdges for amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices taken from the Extreme SuperHyperSet

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

It means that the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Is an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph as used Extreme background in the Extreme terms of worst Extreme case and the common theme of the lower Extreme bound occurred in the specific Extreme SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are Extreme free-quasi-triangle. 924
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Assume an Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme number of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Then every Extreme SuperHyperVertex has at least no Extreme SuperHyperEdge with others in common. Thus those Extreme SuperHyperVertices have the eligibles to be contained in an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. Those Extreme SuperHyperVertices are potentially included in an Extreme style-R-Vertex-Cut. Formally, consider

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

Are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z.$$

where the $\sim$ isn't an equivalence relation but only the symmetric relation on the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The formal definition is as follows.

$$Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z$$

if and only if Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices and there's only and only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ between the Extreme SuperHyperVertices Z_i and Z_j . The other definition for the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ in the terms of Extreme R-Vertex-Cut is

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}.$$

This definition coincides with the definition of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut but with slightly differences in the maximum Extreme cardinality amid those Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$\max_z |\{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \sim Z_j, \quad i \neq j, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}|_{\text{Extreme cardinality}},$$

and

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

is formalized with mathematical literatures on the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. Let $Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j$, be defined as Z_i and Z_j are the Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to the Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. Thus,

$$E = \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid Z_i \stackrel{E}{\sim} Z_j, i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z\}.$$

Or

$$\{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}\}.$$

But with the slightly differences,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Extreme R-Vertex-Cut} = \\ \{Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_z \mid \forall i \neq j, i, j = 1, 2, \dots, z, \exists E_x, Z_i \stackrel{E_x}{\sim} Z_j\}. \end{aligned}$$

Extreme R-Vertex-Cut =

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}}\}.$$

Thus $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is an Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut where $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ is fixed that means $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$. for all Extreme intended SuperHyperVertices but in an Extreme Vertex-Cut, $E_x = E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ could be different and it's not unique. To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. If an Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has z Extreme SuperHyperVertices, then the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut is at least

$$V \setminus (V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots, z_E\}).$$

It's straightforward that the Extreme cardinality of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut is at least the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges with the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges. In other words, the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges contains the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are renamed to Extreme Vertex-Cut in some cases but the maximum number of the Extreme SuperHyperEdge with the maximum Extreme number of Extreme SuperHyperVertices, has the Extreme SuperHyperVertices are contained in an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut.

The obvious SuperHyperGraph has no Extreme SuperHyperEdges. But the non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperModel is up. The quasi-SuperHyperModel addresses some issues about the Extreme optimal SuperHyperObject. It specially delivers some remarks on the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperEdges for distinct amount of Extreme SuperHyperVertices up to all taken from that Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices but this Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices is either has the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality or it doesn't have maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality. In a non-obvious SuperHyperModel, there's at least one Extreme SuperHyperEdge containing at least all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Thus it forms an Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut where the Extreme completion of the Extreme incidence is up in that. Thus it's, literarily, an Extreme embedded R-Vertex-Cut. The SuperHyperNotions of embedded SuperHyperSet and quasi-SuperHyperSet coincide. In the original setting, these types of SuperHyperSets only don't satisfy on the maximum SuperHyperCardinality. Thus the embedded setting is elected such that those SuperHyperSets have the maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality and they're Extreme SuperHyperOptimal. The less than two distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices are included in the minimum Extreme style of the embedded Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. The interior types of the

Extreme SuperHyperVertices are deciders. Since the Extreme number of SuperHyperNeighbors are only affected by the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices. The common connections, more precise and more formal, the perfect unique connections inside the Extreme SuperHyperSet for any distinct types of Extreme SuperHyperVertices pose the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. Thus Extreme exterior SuperHyperVertices could be used only in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and in Extreme SuperHyperRelation with the interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices in that Extreme SuperHyperEdge. In the embedded Extreme Vertex-Cut, there's the usage of exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices since they've more connections inside more than outside. Thus the title "exterior" is more relevant than the title "interior". One Extreme SuperHyperVertex has no connection, inside. Thus, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices with one SuperHyperElement has been ignored in the exploring to lead on the optimal case implying the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. The Extreme R-Vertex-Cut with the exclusion of the exclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge and with other terms, the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut with the inclusion of all Extreme SuperHyperVertices in one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, is an Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut. To sum them up, in a connected non-obvious Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only the maximum possibilities of the distinct interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside of any given Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them. In other words, there's only an unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge $E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has only two distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices in an Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut, minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to some of them but not all of them.

The main definition of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut has two titles. an Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut and its corresponded quasi-maximum Extreme R-SuperHyperCardinality are two titles in the terms of quasi-R-styles. For any Extreme number, there's an Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut with that quasi-maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality in the terms of the embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If there's an embedded Extreme SuperHyperGraph, then the Extreme quasi-SuperHyperNotions lead us to take the collection of all the Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cuts for all Extreme numbers less than its Extreme corresponded maximum number. The essence of the Extreme Vertex-Cut ends up but this essence starts up in the terms of the Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut, again and more in the operations of collecting all the Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cuts acted on the all possible used formations of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph to achieve one Extreme number. This Extreme number is

considered as the equivalence class for all corresponded quasi-R-Vertex-Cuts. Let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}}$ be an Extreme number, an Extreme SuperHyperSet and an Extreme Vertex-Cut. Then

$$\begin{aligned} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} &= \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\ &S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}}, \\ &|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\ &= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}. \end{aligned}$$

As its consequences, the formal definition of the Extreme Vertex-Cut is re-formalized

and redefined as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
&S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}}, \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

To get more precise perceptions, the follow-up expressions propose another formal technical definition for the Extreme Vertex-Cut.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
&S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}}, \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

In more concise and more convenient ways, the modified definition for the Extreme Vertex-Cut poses the upcoming expressions.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

To translate the statement to this mathematical literature, the formulae will be revised.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

And then,

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

To get more visions in the closer look-up, there's an overall overlook.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid \\
&S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}}, \\
&|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} \mid & \\
S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}} = G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}}, & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
\{S \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} \mid & \\
|S_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. &
\end{aligned}$$

Now, the extension of these types of approaches is up. Since the new term, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, could be redefined as the collection of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that any amount of its Extreme SuperHyperVertices are incident to an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. It’s, literarily, another name for “Extreme Quasi-Vertex-Cut” but, precisely, it’s the generalization of “Extreme Quasi-Vertex-Cut” since “Extreme Quasi-Vertex-Cut” happens “Extreme Vertex-Cut” in an Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and background but “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood” may not happens “Extreme Vertex-Cut” in an Extreme SuperHyperGraph as initial framework and preliminarily background since there are some ambiguities about the Extreme SuperHyperCardinality arise from it. To get orderly keywords, the terms, “Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood”, “Extreme Quasi-Vertex-Cut”, and “Extreme Vertex-Cut” are up.

Thus, let $z_{\text{Extreme Number}}$, $N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}$ and $G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}}$ be an Extreme number, an Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood and an Extreme Vertex-Cut and the new terms are up.

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class} &= \\
\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid & \\
|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}| \text{Extreme Cardinality} & \\
= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}] \text{Extreme Class}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}. &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

And with go back to initial structure,

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} = \\
&\cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} \{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&\quad |N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max_{[z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}}} z_{\text{Extreme Number}} \\
&= \max \{ |E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
G_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} &= \\
&\{N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood}} \\
&\in \cup_{z_{\text{Extreme Number}}} [z_{\text{Extreme Number}}]_{\text{Extreme Class}} \mid \\
&|N_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperSet}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} \\
&= \max \{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

To make sense with the precise words in the terms of “R-”, the follow-up illustrations are coming up.

The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut.

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Is an **Extreme R-Vertex-Cut** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there’s no an Extreme SuperHyperEdge amid some Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by **Extreme Vertex-Cut** is related to the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

There’s not only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Vertex-Cut is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Vertex-Cut is an Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

doesn’t have less than two SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet since they’ve come from at least so far an SuperHyperEdge. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}\}} \cdot$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices,

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{xy\}$$

or

$$(V \setminus V \setminus \{x, z\}) \cup \{zy\}$$

is an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph 1041
 $ESHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such 1042
that there's no an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices 1043
instead of all given by that Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Vertex-Cut 1044
and it's an Extreme Vertex-Cut. Since it's 1045

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of 1046
Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for 1047
some amount Extreme SuperHyperVertices instead of all given by that Extreme 1048
type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Vertex-Cut. There isn't only less than two 1049
Extreme SuperHyperVertices inside the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme R-Vertex-Cut,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is up. The non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Vertex-Cut, 1050
not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

does includes only less than two SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme 1046
SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ but it's impossible in the case, they've corresponded 1047
to an SuperHyperEdge. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple 1048
Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the 1049

“Extreme R-Vertex-Cut”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the 1050

Extreme R-Vertex-Cut,

is only and only 1051

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ with a illustrated 1052
SuperHyperModeling. It's also, not only an Extreme free-triangle embedded 1053
SuperHyperModel and an Extreme on-triangle embedded SuperHyperModel but also 1054
it's an Extreme stable embedded SuperHyperModel. But all only non-obvious simple 1055
Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut amid those obvious simple 1056
Extreme type-SuperHyperSets of the Extreme Vertex-Cut, are

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$.

To sum them up, assume a connected loopless Extreme SuperHyperGraph 1057
 $ESHG : (V, E)$. Then in the worst case, literally,

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

is an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. In other words, the least cardinality, the lower sharp bound for the cardinality, of an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut is the cardinality of

$$V \setminus V \setminus \{a_E, b_E, c_E, \dots\}_{E=\{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \mid |E|=\max\{|E| \mid E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}} \cdot$$

To sum them up, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices belong to any Extreme quasi-R-Vertex-Cut if for any of them, and any of other corresponded Extreme SuperHyperVertex, some interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices are mutually Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors with no Extreme exception at all minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to any amount of them.

Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Let an Extreme SuperHyperEdge $ESHE : E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}$ has some Extreme SuperHyperVertices r . Consider all Extreme numbers of those Extreme SuperHyperVertices from that Extreme SuperHyperEdge excluding excluding more than r distinct Extreme SuperHyperVertices, exclude to any given Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices. Consider there's an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut with the least cardinality, the lower sharp Extreme bound for Extreme cardinality. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \setminus \{z\}$ is an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely but it isn't an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. Since it doesn't have

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some SuperHyperVertices uniquely. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices but it isn't an Extreme R-Vertex-Cut. Since it **doesn't do** the Extreme procedure such that such that there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely [there are at least one Extreme SuperHyperVertex outside implying there's, sometimes in the connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$, an Extreme SuperHyperVertex, titled its Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, to that Extreme SuperHyperVertex in the Extreme SuperHyperSet S so as S doesn't do "the Extreme procedure" .]. There's only **one** Extreme SuperHyperVertex **outside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet, $V_{ESHE} \cup \{z\}$, in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhood. Thus the obvious Extreme R-Vertex-Cut, V_{ESHE} is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme R-Vertex-Cut, V_{ESHE} , **is** an Extreme SuperHyperSet, V_{ESHE} , **includes** only **all** Extreme SuperHyperVertices does forms any kind of Extreme pairs are titled Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices V_{ESHE} , is the **maximum Extreme SuperHyperCardinality** of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices **such that** there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge to have some Extreme SuperHyperVertices uniquely. Thus, in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. Any Extreme R-Vertex-Cut only contains all interior Extreme SuperHyperVertices and all exterior Extreme SuperHyperVertices from the unique Extreme SuperHyperEdge where there's any of them has all possible Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors in and there's all Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhoods in with no exception minus all Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors to some of them not all of them but everything is possible about Extreme SuperHyperNeighborhoods and Extreme SuperHyperNeighbors out.

The SuperHyperNotion, namely, Vertex-Cut, is up. There's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. The following Extreme SuperHyperSet of

Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Vertex-Cut. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

is the simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Vertex-Cut. The Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an **Extreme Vertex-Cut** $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an Extreme type-SuperHyperSet with

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme SuperHyperVertex of an Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There are not only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious Extreme Vertex-Cut is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Vertex-Cut is an Extreme SuperHyperSet **includes** only **two** Extreme SuperHyperVertices. But the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Doesn't have less than three SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet. Thus the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Vertex-Cut **is** up. To sum them up, the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the

Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices],

1121

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Vertex-Cut. 1122

Since the Extreme SuperHyperSet of the Extreme 1123

SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices], 1124

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is an Extreme Vertex-Cut $\mathcal{C}(ESHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$ 1125

is the Extreme SuperHyperSet S of Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that there's no 1126

an Extreme SuperHyperEdge for some Extreme SuperHyperVertices given by that 1127

Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the Extreme Vertex-Cut **and** it's an Extreme 1128

Vertex-Cut. Since it's 1129

the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of 1130

Extreme SuperHyperEdges[SuperHyperVertices] such that there's no Extreme 1131

SuperHyperVertex of an Extreme SuperHyperEdge is common and there's an Extreme 1132

SuperHyperEdge for all Extreme SuperHyperVertices. There aren't only less than three 1133

Extreme SuperHyperVertices **inside** the intended Extreme SuperHyperSet, 1134

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the non-obvious Extreme Vertex-Cut, 1135

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is up. The obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet of the Extreme Vertex-Cut, not:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Is the Extreme SuperHyperSet, not:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

Does includes only less than three SuperHyperVertices in a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. It's interesting to mention that the only non-obvious simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSet called the

“Extreme Vertex-Cut”

amid those obvious[non-obvious] simple Extreme type-SuperHyperSets called the

Extreme Vertex-Cut,

is only and only

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-Cut} \\
&= \{E_{2i-1}\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeQuasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} \\
&= 2z^{\lfloor \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}}{2} \rfloor} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-Cut} = \{V_i\}_{i=1}^s, \{V_j\}_{j=1}^t \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{ExtremeR-Quasi-Vertex-CutSuperHyperPolynomial} = az^s + bz^t.
\end{aligned}$$

In a connected Extreme SuperHyperGraph $ESHG : (V, E)$. □

5 The Extreme Departures on The Theoretical Results Toward Theoretical Motivations

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses.

Proposition 5.1. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 1151

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{E_i\}_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|} z^{|E_i|}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
&= \{V_{E_i}\}_{|E_i|=1}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{i \neq 1, |E_{NSHG}|, |E_i|=1} z^{|V_i|}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1152

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}
\end{aligned}$$

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
& E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. 1154
There's a new way to redefine as 1155

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 1156
corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is 1157
straightforward. $\square$ 1158

Example 5.2. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath 1159
 $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the 1160
Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1161

Proposition 5.3. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. 1162

Figure 23. an Extreme SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Example (16.5)

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}, V_{\lfloor \frac{|E_{NSHG}|}{3} \rfloor}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.

Figure 24. an Extreme SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.7)

There's a new way to redefine as

1167

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. □ 1170

Example 5.4. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1171
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Proposition 5.5. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then 1174

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Vertex-Cut}} &= \{\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 0z^0. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-Vertex-Cut}} &= \{CENTER\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{|CENTER|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 CENTER, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 25. an Extreme SuperHyperStar Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.9)

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$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 5.6. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

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Proposition 5.7. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.

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Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
& = \{ \} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 0z^0. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
& = \{ \{ \text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices} \} \}, \\
& = \{ \} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 0z^0.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& E_1, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
& E_2, V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperVertex-Cut could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

Figure 26. Extreme SuperHyperBipartite Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Example (16.11)

The latter is straightforward. □ 1202

Example 5.8. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1203
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Proposition 5.9. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then 1209
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$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{ \} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{ \{ \text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices} \} \}, \\
 &= \{ \} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1211

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\
E_2, V_2^{EXTERNAL}, \\
\cdots, \\
E_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}, V_{|P_i|=\min_{P_j \in E_{NSHG}} |P_j|}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperVertex-Cut could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 5.10. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

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Proposition 5.11. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$.

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Figure 27. an Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Example (16.13)

Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut}} \\
 &= \{\{ \text{One From Every MATCHING SuperHyperVertices} \}, \\
 &= \{\} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme V-Vertex-Cut SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= 0z^0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1^*, \\
 & \text{CENTER}, E_2^*
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & E_1^*, V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \\
 & E_2^*, \text{CENTER}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The latter is

Figure 28. an Extreme SuperHyperWheel Extreme Associated to the Extreme Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in the Extreme Example (16.15)

straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperVertex-Cut could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperVertex-Cut proposes some longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 5.12. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

6 The Surveys of Mathematical Sets On The Results But As The Initial Motivation

For the SuperHyperVertex-Cut, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, and the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, some general results are introduced.

Remark 6.1. Let remind that the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut is “redefined” on the positions of the alphabets.

Corollary 6.2. Assume Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Extreme SuperHyperVertex - Cut} = \\ & \{ \text{the SuperHyperVertex - Cut of the SuperHyperVertices} \mid \\ & \max | \text{SuperHyperOffensive} \\ & \text{SuperHyperVertex - Cut} \\ & | \text{Extremecardinalityamidthose SuperHyperVertex - Cut.} \} \end{aligned}$$

plus one Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor to one. Where σ_i is the unary operation on the SuperHyperVertices of the SuperHyperGraph to assign the determinacy, the indeterminacy and the neutrality, for $i = 1, 2, 3$, respectively.

Corollary 6.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then the notion of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut and SuperHyperVertex-Cut coincide.

Corollary 6.4. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a conseNeighborive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is an Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut if and only if it's a SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1262
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Corollary 6.5. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then a conseNeighborive sequence of the SuperHyperVertices is a strongest SuperHyperVertex-Cut if and only if it's a longest SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1265
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Corollary 6.6. Assume SuperHyperClasses of an Extreme SuperHyperGraph on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut is its SuperHyperVertex-Cut and reversely. 1268
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Corollary 6.7. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel) on the same identical letter of the alphabet. Then its Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut is its SuperHyperVertex-Cut and reversely. 1271
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Corollary 6.8. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then its Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined. 1275
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Corollary 6.9. Assume SuperHyperClasses of an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then its Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined. 1278
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Corollary 6.10. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut isn't well-defined. 1281
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Corollary 6.11. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then its Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined. 1285
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Corollary 6.12. Assume SuperHyperClasses of an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then its Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined. 1288
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Corollary 6.13. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). Then its Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined if and only if its SuperHyperVertex-Cut is well-defined. 1291
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Proposition 6.14. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then V is 1295

(i) : the dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1296

(ii) : the strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1297

(iii) : the connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1298

(iv) : the δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1299

(v) : the strong δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1300

(vi) : the connected δ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1301

Proposition 6.15. Let $NTG : (V, E, \sigma, \mu)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then $\emptyset$ is 1302

(i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1303

(ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1304

(iii) : the connected defensive SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1305

(iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1306

(v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1307

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1308

Proposition 6.16. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then an independent SuperHyperSet is 1309

(i) : the SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1311

(ii) : the strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1312

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1313

(iv) : the δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1314

(v) : the strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1315

(vi) : the connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1316

Proposition 6.17. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperVertex-Cut/SuperHyperPath. Then V is a maximal 1317

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1320

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1321

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1322

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1323

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1324

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1325

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1326

Proposition 6.18. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperWheel. Then V is a maximal 1327

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1329

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1330

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1331

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1332

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1333

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1334

Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1335

Proposition 6.19. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperVertex-Cut/SuperHyperPath. Then the number of*

(i) : the SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1339

(ii) : the SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1340

(iii) : the connected SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1341

(iv) : the $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1342

(v) : the strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1343

(vi) : the connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1344

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1345
1346

Proposition 6.20. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperWheel. Then the number of*

(i) : the dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1349

(ii) : the dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1350

(iii) : the dual connected SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1351

(iv) : the dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1352

(v) : the strong dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1353

(vi) : the connected dual $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ -SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1354

is one and it's only V . Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1355
1356

Proposition 6.21. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices is a*

(i) : dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1362

(ii) : strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1363

(iii) : connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1364

(iv) : $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1365

(v) : strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1366

(vi) : connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1367

Proposition 6.22. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then a SuperHyperSet contains the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices in the biggest SuperHyperPart is a*

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1374

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1375

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1376

(iv) : *δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1377

(v) : *strong δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1378

(vi) : *connected δ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*. 1379

Proposition 6.23. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperUniform SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperStar/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperBipartite/SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperMultipartite. Then the number of* 1380
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1383

(i) : *dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1384

(ii) : *strong dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1385

(iii) : *connected dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1386

(iv) : *$\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1387

(v) : *strong $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1388

(vi) : *connected $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG)}{2} + 1$ -dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*. 1389

is one and it's only S , a SuperHyperSet contains [the SuperHyperCenter and] the half of multiplying r with the number of all the SuperHyperEdges plus one of all the SuperHyperVertices. Where the exterior SuperHyperVertices and the interior SuperHyperVertices coincide. 1390
1391
1392
1393

Proposition 6.24. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. The number of connected component is $|V - S|$ if there's a SuperHyperSet which is a dual* 1394
1395

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1396

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1397

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1398

(iv) : *SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1399

(v) : *strong 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1400

(vi) : *connected 1-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*. 1401

Proposition 6.25. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then the number is at most $\mathcal{O}(ESHG)$ and the Extreme number is at most $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG)$.* 1402
1403

Proposition 6.26. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}} \sigma(v)$, in the setting of dual* 1404
1405
1406

(i) : *SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1407

(ii) : *strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1408

(iii) : *connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut*; 1409

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1410

(v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1411

(vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1412

Proposition 6.27. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is $\emptyset$. The number is 0 and the Extreme number is 0, for an independent SuperHyperSet in the setting of dual 1413
1414
1415

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1416

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1417

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1418

(iv) : 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1419

(v) : strong 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1420

(vi) : connected 0-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1421

Proposition 6.28. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperComplete. Then there's no independent SuperHyperSet. 1422
1423

Proposition 6.29. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperVertex-Cut/SuperHyperPath/SuperHyperWheel. The number is $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ and the Extreme number is $\mathcal{O}_n(ESHG : (V, E))$, in the setting of a dual 1424
1425
1426
1427

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1428

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1429

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1430

(iv) : $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1431

(v) : strong $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1432

(vi) : connected $\mathcal{O}(ESHG : (V, E))$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1433

Proposition 6.30. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is SuperHyperStar/complete SuperHyperBipartite/complete SuperHyperMultiPartite. The number is $\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1$ and the Extreme number is $\min \sum_{v \in \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_t\}_{t > \frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2}}} \subseteq V \sigma(v)$, in the setting of a dual 1434
1435
1436
1437

(i) : SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1438

(ii) : strong SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1439

(iii) : connected SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1440

(iv) : $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1441

(v) : strong $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1442

(vi) : connected $(\frac{\mathcal{O}(ESHG:(V,E))}{2} + 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1443

Proposition 6.31. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a SuperHyperFamily of the ESHGs : (V, E) Extreme SuperHyperGraphs which are from one-type SuperHyperClass which the result is obtained for the individuals. Then the results also hold for the SuperHyperFamily $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ of these specific SuperHyperClasses of the Extreme SuperHyperGraphs.

Proposition 6.32. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then $\forall v \in V \setminus S, \exists x \in S$ such that

(i) $v \in N_s(x)$;

(ii) $vx \in E$.

Proposition 6.33. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. If S is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then

(i) S is SuperHyperVertex-Cut set;

(ii) there's $S \subseteq S'$ such that $|S'|$ is SuperHyperChromatic number.

Proposition 6.34. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O}$;

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n$.

Proposition 6.35. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is connected. Then

(i) $\Gamma \leq \mathcal{O} - 1$;

(ii) $\Gamma_s \leq \mathcal{O}_n - \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(x)$.

Proposition 6.36. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperPath. Then

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$;

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only a dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Proposition 6.37. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperPath. Then

(i) the set $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$;

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$;

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut.

Proposition 6.38. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Then

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut;

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ and corresponded SuperHyperSets are $\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1480
1481

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S=\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}} \sigma(s), \sum_{s \in S=\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sigma(s)\}$; 1482

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_n\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1483
1484

Proposition 6.39. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperVertex-Cut. Then 1485

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1486
1487

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ and corresponded SuperHyperSet is $S = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$; 1488

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S=\{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s), \sum_{s \in S=\{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}$; 1489

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S_1 = \{v_2, v_4, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ and $S_2 = \{v_1, v_3, \dots, v_{n-1}\}$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1490
1491

Proposition 6.40. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperStar. Then 1492

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c\}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1493

(ii) $\Gamma = 1$; 1494

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(c)$; 1495

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1496

Proposition 6.41. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be SuperHyperWheel. Then 1497

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1498
1499

(ii) $\Gamma = |\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}|$; 1500

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)$; 1501

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $\{v_1, v_3\} \cup \{v_6, v_9, \dots, v_{i+6}, \dots, v_n\}_{i=1}^{6+3(i-1) \leq n}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1502
1503

Proposition 6.42. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an odd SuperHyperComplete. Then 1504

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1505
1506

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$; 1507

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$; 1508

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is only a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1509
1510

Proposition 6.43. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be an even SuperHyperComplete. Then 1511

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1512
1513

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$; 1514

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$; 1515

(iv) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is only a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1516
1517

Proposition 6.44. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of Extreme SuperHyperStars with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1518
1519

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1520
1521

(ii) $\Gamma = m$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1522

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^3 \sigma_j(c_i)$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1523

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ and $S \subset S'$ are only dual SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1524
1525

Proposition 6.45. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be an m -SuperHyperFamily of odd SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1526
1527
1528

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ is a dual maximal SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF}$; 1529
1530

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1531

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1532

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}$ are only a dual maximal SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1533
1534

Proposition 6.46. Let $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$ be a m -SuperHyperFamily of even SuperHyperComplete SuperHyperGraphs with common Extreme SuperHyperVertex SuperHyperSet. Then 1535
1536
1537

(i) the SuperHyperSet $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ is a dual SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1538
1539

(ii) $\Gamma = \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1540

(iii) $\Gamma_s = \min\{\sum_{s \in S} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sigma_i(s)\}_{S=\{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}}$ for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$; 1541

(iv) the SuperHyperSets $S = \{v_i\}_{i=1}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor}$ are only dual maximal SuperHyperVertex-Cut for $\mathcal{NSHF} : (V, E)$. 1542
1543

Proposition 6.47. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1544
1545

(i) if $s \geq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then S is an s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1546
1547
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(ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1549
1550
1551

Proposition 6.48. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a strong Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1552
1553

- (i) if $s \geq t + 2$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is an t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then S is an s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1554
1555
1556
- (ii) if $s \leq t$ and a SuperHyperSet S of SuperHyperVertices is a dual t -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut, then S is a dual s -SuperHyperPowerful SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1557
1558
1559

Proposition 6.49. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ be a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1560
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1562

- (i) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1563
1564
- (ii) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1565
1566
- (iii) if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1567
1568
- (iv) if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1569
1570

Proposition 6.50. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph. Then following statements hold; 1571
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1573

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1574
1575
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1576
1577
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1578
1579
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual V -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1580
1581

Proposition 6.51. Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a $[an]$ $[V-]$ SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph which is a SuperHyperComplete. Then following statements hold; 1582
1583
1584

- (i) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1585
1586
- (ii) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual 2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1587
1588
- (iii) $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut; 1589
1590
- (iv) $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)$ -SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1591
1592

Proposition 6.52. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph$ which is a $SuperHyperComplete$. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (ii) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > \lfloor \frac{\mathcal{O}-1}{2} \rfloor + 1$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (iii) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is $(\mathcal{O} - 1)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (iv) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $(\mathcal{O} - 1)-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$.*

Proposition 6.53. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph$ which is $SuperHyperVertex-Cut$. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *$\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (ii) *$\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (iii) *$\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (iv) *$\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$ if $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$.*

Proposition 6.54. *Let $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a[an] $[V-]SuperHyperUniform-strong-Extreme SuperHyperGraph$ which is $SuperHyperVertex-Cut$. Then following statements hold;*

- (i) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap S| < 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (ii) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap S| > 2$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (iii) *if $\forall a \in S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is an $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$;*
- (iv) *if $\forall a \in V \setminus S, |N_s(a) \cap V \setminus S| = 0$, then $ESHG : (V, E)$ is a dual $2-SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperVertex-Cut$.*

7 Extreme Applications in Cancer's Extreme Recognition

The cancer is the Extreme disease but the Extreme model is going to figure out what's going on this Extreme phenomenon. The special Extreme case of this Extreme disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Extreme recognition of the cancer could help to find some Extreme treatments for this Extreme disease.

In the following, some Extreme steps are Extreme devised on this disease.

Figure 29. an Extreme SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut

Step 1. (Extreme Definition) The Extreme recognition of the cancer in the long-term Extreme function. 1635 1636

Step 2. (Extreme Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Extreme model [it's called Extreme SuperHyperGraph] and the long Extreme cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Extreme SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done. 1637 1638 1639 1640 1641 1642 1643

Step 3. (Extreme Model) There are some specific Extreme models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Extreme models. The moves and the Extreme traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by an Extreme SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperVertex-Cut, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut or the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut in those Extreme Extreme SuperHyperModels. 1644 1645 1646 1647 1648 1649 1650 1651

8 Case 1: The Initial Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperBipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel 1652 1653 1654

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (29), the Extreme SuperHyperBipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. By using the Extreme Figure (29) and the Table (4), the Extreme SuperHyperBipartite is obtained. 1655 1656 1657 1658

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 30. an Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut

The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous
 Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (29), is
 the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1659
1660
1661
1662

9 Case 2: The Increasing Extreme Steps Toward Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite as Extreme SuperHyperModel 1663 1664 1665

Step 4. (Extreme Solution) In the Extreme Figure (30), the Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. 1666
 By using the Extreme Figure (30) and the Table (5), the Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. 1667
1668
1669
 The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous
 result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
 SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (30),
 is the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut. 1670
1671
1672
1673

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut?*

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut?*

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperVertex-Cut, are there else?*

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 10.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, concluding remarks and closing remarks are represented. The drawbacks of this research are illustrated. Some benefits and some advantages of this research are highlighted.

This research uses some approaches to make Extreme SuperHyperGraphs more understandable. In this endeavor, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the SuperHyperVertex-Cut. For that sake in the second definition, the main definition of the Extreme SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new definition for the Extreme SuperHyperGraph, the new SuperHyperNotion, Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut, finds the convenient background to implement some results based on that. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Extreme SuperHyperClasses are the cases of this research on the modeling of the regions where are under the attacks of the cancer to recognize this disease as it’s mentioned on the title “Cancer’s Recognitions”. To formalize the instances on the SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperVertex-Cut, the new SuperHyperClasses and SuperHyperClasses, are introduced. Some general results are gathered in the section on the SuperHyperVertex-Cut and the Extreme

SuperHyperVertex-Cut. The clarifications, instances and literature reviews have taken the whole way through. In this research, the literature reviews have fulfilled the lines containing the notions and the results. The SuperHyperGraph and Extreme SuperHyperGraph are the SuperHyperModels on the “Cancer’s Recognitions” and both bases are the background of this research. Sometimes the cancer has been happened on the region, full of cells, groups of cells and embedded styles. In this segment, the SuperHyperModel proposes some SuperHyperNotions based on the connectivities of the moves of the cancer in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of the design and the architecture are formally called “ SuperHyperVertex-Cut” in the themes of jargons and buzzwords. The prefix “SuperHyper” refers to the theme of the embedded styles to figure out the background for the SuperHyperNotions. In the Table (6),

Table 6. An Overlook On This Research And Beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining Extreme SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. SuperHyperVertex-Cut	
3. Extreme SuperHyperVertex-Cut	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. Modeling of Cancer’s Recognitions	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

benefits and avenues for this research are, figured out, pointed out and spoken out.

12 Extreme SuperHyperDuality But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 12.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperDuality).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall E_i \in E', \exists E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E'$ such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$ and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality** if $\forall V_i \in V', \exists V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V'$ such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$ and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it’s either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality.

Definition 12.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperDuality). 1742

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an 1743
 Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 1744

(i) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1745
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1746
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1747
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1748
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1749
 SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme 1750
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1751
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1752

(ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, 1753
 Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme 1754
 rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph 1755
 $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1756
 SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality 1757
 conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices 1758
 such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1759

(iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1760
 Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1761
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1762
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1763
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1764
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of 1765
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive 1766
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form 1767
 the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its 1768
 Extreme coefficient; 1769

(iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of 1770
 Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1771
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1772
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme 1773
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme 1774
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of 1775
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive 1776
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form 1777
 the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its 1778
 Extreme coefficient; 1779

(v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1780
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1781
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1782
 Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality 1783
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme 1784
 SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme 1785
 SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the 1786
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality; 1787

(vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality** if it's either of Extreme 1788
 e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme 1789
 v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an 1790

Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality;

(vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

(viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme re-SuperHyperDuality, Extreme v-SuperHyperDuality, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperDuality and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperDuality; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 12.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in

every given Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1832

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1833
1834

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1835
1836

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1837
1838

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1839
1840

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{3i+24_{i=0}^3}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^7}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1841
1842

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1843
1844

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1845
1846

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{23}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, V_{15}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1847
1848

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1849
1850

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1, E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_6, V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1851
1852

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5, 7, 8}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1853
1854

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_5, E_9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &3 \times 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1855
1856

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1857
1858

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1859
1860

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 1 \times 2) + (2 \times 4 \times 5)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1861
1862

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(1 \times 1 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1863
1864

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &(2 \times 2 \times 2)z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1865
1866

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1867
1868

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1869
1870

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperDuality, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 1871
1872

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 9 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 9 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 1873
1874

Proposition 12.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 1875
1876

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1877

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperDuality} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperDuality} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperDuality\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &= \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}, E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} |z|. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 12.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality.

Proposition 12.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E_i \in E_{P_i, ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ & z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. 1913
 There's a new way to redefine as 1914

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 1915
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 1916
 straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi 1917
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. 1918
 There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one 1919
 SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the 1920

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite 1921
 $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only 1922
 minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 1923

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □ 1924

Example 12.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme 1925
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. 1926
 The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme 1927
 result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme 1928
 SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the 1929
 Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1930

Proposition 12.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 1931

$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
&= \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\
& \quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} \\
&= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
&= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
\end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 1944

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 1945
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 1946

Example 12.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 1947
 $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme 1948
SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme 1949
SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, 1950
in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1951

Proposition 12.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. 1952
Then, 1953

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{E^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i | E_i^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}} |z|. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ R-Quasi-SuperHyperDuality SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 1954

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\
 V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2^*, \\
 \dots, \\
 E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}, V_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDuality taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel 1955
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 1956

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z^* \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z^* \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z^*.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 1957
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperDuality. The latter is 1958
straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperDuality. Thus the notion of quasi 1959
isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperDuality could be applied. 1960
The unique embedded SuperHyperDuality proposes some longest SuperHyperDuality 1961
excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$ 1962

Example 12.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme 1963
SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained 1964
Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme 1965
SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in 1966
the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperDuality. 1967

13 Extreme SuperHyperJoin But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 13.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperJoin).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin.

Definition 13.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperJoin).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

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- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin;

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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

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- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme re-SuperHyperJoin, Extreme v-SuperHyperJoin, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperJoin and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperJoin; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

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Example 13.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme

SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperJoin. 2063
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperJoin. 2068
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2076
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_2, V_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2078
2079

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2080
2081

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2082
2083

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{3i+24^3_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1^7_{i=0}}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 6z^8.$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2084
2085

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2086
2087

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2088
2089

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, E_{23}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{3i+1^3_{i=0}}, V_{15}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2090
2091

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_3, V_{13}, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 4 \times 5 \times 5z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2092
2093

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1, E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_6, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2094
2095

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2096
2097

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_3, E_9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2098
2099

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2100
2101

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2102
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2104
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \{E_2, E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} = \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2106
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2108
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2110
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2112
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperJoin, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2114
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E_2, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2116
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Proposition 13.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. 2118

Then

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \frac{|\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{|\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \frac{|\mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |\mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} \frac{|\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& \mathcal{V}_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \mathcal{E}_1, \\
& \mathcal{V}_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \mathcal{E}_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& \mathcal{E}_{|\frac{|\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}|}, \mathcal{V}_{|\frac{|\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}|}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim \mathcal{V}_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! \mathcal{E}_z \in \mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \mathcal{V}_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in \mathcal{E}_z \equiv \\
& \exists! \mathcal{E}_z \in \mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{\mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, \mathcal{V}_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq \mathcal{E}_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(\mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(\mathcal{V}_j)|$ where $\mathcal{V}_j$ is
corresponded to $\mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is
straightforward. □

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Example 13.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath
 $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the
Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$.
Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin}} = \\
& = \frac{|\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z \frac{|\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin}} \\
& = \frac{|\mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}}{3} \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |\mathcal{V}_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} \frac{|\mathcal{E}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V^{EXTERNAL} \frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}.
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}|z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE}). \end{aligned}$$

{},

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}). \end{aligned}$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)$$

$$z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= (\text{OTHERWISE})0. \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied.

There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{EXTERNAL} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 13.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin}}$$

$$= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperJoin SuperHyperPolynomial}}$$

$$= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one

SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 13.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

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Proposition 13.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin} = \\
 &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin} \\
 &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}. \\
 &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperJoin\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}}{3}}^{EXTERNAL}.
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperJoin taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperJoin. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperJoin. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperJoin could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperJoin proposes some longest SuperHyperJoin excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 13.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperJoin.

14 Extreme SuperHyperPerfect But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 14.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect.

Definition 14.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperPerfect).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph

- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2237-2241
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2242-2248
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2249-2258
- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient; 2259-2268
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2269-2276
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; 2277-2283
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme 2284-2285

v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient;

- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme re-SuperHyperPerfect, Extreme v-SuperHyperPerfect, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperPerfect and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its Extreme coefficient.

Example 14.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , **is** excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme

SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2323

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2324 2325

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 15z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2326 2327

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2328 2329

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1}_{i=0}^3, E_{3i+24}_{i=0}^3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{3i+1}_{i=0}^7\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 6z^8.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2330 2331

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{15}, E_{16}, E_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2332 2333

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2334
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, E_{23}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_{3i+1_{i=0}^3}, V_{15}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z^5.$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2336
2337

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_5\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_3, V_6, V_8\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2338
2339

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1, E_3\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_6, V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 2z^2.$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2340
2341

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_{i=4}^{i \neq 5,7,8}\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 5z^5.$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2342
2343

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_3, E_9\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1, V_6\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3 \times 3z^2.$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2344
2345

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_1\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2346
2347

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2348
2349

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 5 \times 5) + (1 \times 2 + 1)z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2350
2351

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2352
2353

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{27}, V_2, V_7, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (1 \times 1 \times 2 + 1)z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2354
2355

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_{3i+1_{i=0^3}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_{2i+1_{i=0^5}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^6.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2356
2357

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2358
2359

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperPerfect, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2360
2361

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{E_2, E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_3, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10 \times 6 + 10 \times 6 + 12 \times 6 + 12 \times 6z^2. \end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2362
2363

Proposition 14.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. Then 2364
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$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}|_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2366

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2367
2368

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2369
2370
2371 $\square$

Example 14.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperPerfect. 2372
2373
2374

Proposition 14.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2375
2376

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = 3z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} \\
& = \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2377

$$\begin{aligned}
& P : \\
& V_1^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_1, \\
& V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\
& \dots, \\
& E_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}, V_{\frac{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}}{3}}^{\text{EXTERNAL}}.
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2378
2379

$$\begin{aligned}
& V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z \equiv \\
& \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to V_i^{EXTERNAL} in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. 2380
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2382 $\square$

Example 14.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect. 2383
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Proposition 14.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then 2386
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$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
& = |i | E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} | z. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 14.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

Proposition 14.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \\ &\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= (OTHERWISE). \\ &\{\}, \\ &If\ \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= (PERFECT\ MATCHING). \\ &= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) choose |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right) \\ &\quad z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ &where\ \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= (OTHERWISE)0. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect} \\ &= \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| choose 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$.
There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is
corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is
straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of
quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be
applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have
one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite
 $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only
minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

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Example 14.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme
SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured.
The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme
result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme
SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the
Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$\{E_i \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = (\text{OTHERWISE}).$$

$\{\}$,

$$\text{If } \exists P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \neq \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{PERFECT MATCHING}).$$

$$= \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|) \text{choose } |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \right)_{z^{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}}$$

$$\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = (\text{OTHERWISE})0.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect}} = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{EXTERNAL}}, V_i^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, i \neq j\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperPerfect SuperHyperPolynomial}} = \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ \dots, \\ E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}} \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have

one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

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minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

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$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 &V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 &V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 &\dots, \\
 &E_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|}, V_{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|+1}^{EXTERNAL}
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite

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$ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme

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SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme

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SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$,

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in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

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Proposition 14.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$.

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Then,

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$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{E \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= |i \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} |z. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperPerfect\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

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$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, V_j^{EXTERNAL}.$$

is a longest SuperHyperPerfect taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel

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$ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

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$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} &\subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is

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corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperPerfect. The latter is

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straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperPerfect. Thus the notion of quasi

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isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperPerfect could be applied. The

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unique embedded SuperHyperPerfect proposes some longest SuperHyperPerfect excerpt

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from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

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Example 14.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperPerfect.

15 Extreme SuperHyperTotal But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 15.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperTotal).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal** if $\forall V_i \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \exists! V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal.

Definition 15.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperTotal).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;

- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
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- Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
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- v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
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- Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
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- SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
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- number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
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- an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
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- Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
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- the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
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- Extreme coefficient;
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- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
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- Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
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- v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
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- Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
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- SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
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- number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
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- an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
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- Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
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- the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
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- Extreme coefficient;
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- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal,
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- Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme
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- rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
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- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme
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- SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
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- in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and
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- Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal,
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- Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme
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- rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph
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- $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme
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- SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality
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- conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices
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- such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperTotal;
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- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
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- Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
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- v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
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- Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
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- SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
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- number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
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- of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
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- Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
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- the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
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- Extreme coefficient;
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- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
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- Extreme e-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme re-SuperHyperTotal, Extreme
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- v-SuperHyperTotal, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperTotal and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an
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- Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
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- SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
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- number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
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of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperTotal; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient.

Example 15.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$
 in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items.

- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme
 SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of
 Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely,
 E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no
 Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme
 SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.
 E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme
 SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's
 only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex,
 V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as
 an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in
 every given Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme
 SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-}} = \{E_4, E_2\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 2z^2.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2570
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2572
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2574
2575

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2576
2577

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2578
2579

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2580
2581

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2582
2583

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2584
2585

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2586
2587

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2588
2589

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2590
2591

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2592
2593

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2594
2595

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2596
2597

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2598
2599

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2600
2601

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_6, E_{10}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= (|V| - 1)z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2602
2603

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_1, V_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 9z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperTotal, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2604
2605

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2606
2607

Proposition 15.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2608
2609

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} \\
& = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2610

$$\begin{aligned}
P : \\
V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
\dots
\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2611
2612

$$\begin{aligned}
V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} & \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} & \in E_z \equiv \\
\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} & \subseteq E_z.
\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. 2613
2614
2615 $\square$

Example 15.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperTotal. 2616
2617
2618

Proposition 15.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then 2619
2620

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} = \\
& = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\
& z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} \\
& = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}. \\
& \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
& = \prod |V_i^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}-2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 P : \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\
 & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\
 & \dots, \\
 & \frac{E^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1} V^{EXTERNAL}}{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\
 &= |i(i-1)| E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} |z^2. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal}} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\
 \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\
 &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1) \\
 &z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 15.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z \min_{|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperTotal}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperTotal SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 15.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESH B : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal.

Proposition 15.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i ESHG:(V,E)}, \\
 & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= z^{\min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\
 & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\
 &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} \\
 &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\
 & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\
 &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned}
 & P : \\
 & V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\
 & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only

minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution 2677

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2678
 $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □ 2679

Example 15.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite 2680
 $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme 2681
 SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme 2682
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, 2683
 in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2684

Proposition 15.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. 2685
 Then, 2686

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal} &= \{E_i, E_j \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i(i-1) \mid E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal} &= \{CENTER, V_j \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ R-SuperHyperTotal\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= \\ &(|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}) \text{ choose } (|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ &z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2687

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperTotal taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel 2688
 $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2689

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is 2690
 corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperTotal. The latter is 2691
 straightforward. Then there's at least one SuperHyperTotal. Thus the notion of quasi 2692
 isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperTotal could be applied. The 2693
 unique embedded SuperHyperTotal proposes some longest SuperHyperTotal excerpt 2694
 from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. □ 2695

Example 15.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme 2696
 SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained 2697
 Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme 2698
 SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, 2699
 in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperTotal. 2700

16 Extreme SuperHyperConnected But As The Extensions Excerpt From Dense And Super Forms

Definition 16.1. (Different Extreme Types of Extreme SuperHyperConnected).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperSet $V' = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$ and $E' = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_z\}$. Then either V' or E' is called

- (i) **Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; and $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$;
- (ii) **Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus E', \exists E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \in E_i, E_j$; $\forall E_i, E_j \in E'$, such that $V_a \notin E_i, E_j$; and $|E_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |E_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (iii) **Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$;
- (iv) **Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected** if $\forall V_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)} \setminus V', \exists V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \in E_a$; $\forall V_i, V_j \in V'$, such that $V_i, V_j \notin E_a$; and $|V_i|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}} = |V_j|_{\text{NEUTROSOPIC CARDINALITY}}$;
- (v) **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected.

Definition 16.2. ((Extreme) SuperHyperConnected).

Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider an Extreme SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

- (i) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (ii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for a Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (iii) an **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of

an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient;

- (iv) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$
 for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperEdges of
 an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient;
- (v) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme
 e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$
 for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme
 cardinality of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality of the
 Extreme SuperHyperVertices in the conseNeighborive Extreme sequence of
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperConnected;
- (vi) a **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected** if it's either of Extreme
 e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$
 for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the maximum Extreme
 cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of
 high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive Extreme SuperHyperEdges and
 Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form the Extreme
 SuperHyperConnected;
- (vii) an **Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's
 either of Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected,
 Extreme v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and
 $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$ for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient;
- (viii) a **Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial** if it's either of
 Extreme e-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme re-SuperHyperConnected, Extreme
 v-SuperHyperConnected, and Extreme rv-SuperHyperConnected and $\mathcal{C}(NSHG)$
 for an Extreme SuperHyperGraph $NSHG : (V, E)$ is the Extreme
 SuperHyperPolynomial contains the Extreme coefficients defined as the Extreme
 number of the maximum Extreme cardinality of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices
 of an Extreme SuperHyperSet S of high Extreme cardinality conseNeighborive
 Extreme SuperHyperEdges and Extreme SuperHyperVertices such that they form
 the Extreme SuperHyperConnected; and the Extreme power is corresponded to its
 Extreme coefficient.

Example 16.3. Assume an Extreme SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Extreme Figures in every Extreme items. 2796
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- On the Figure (1), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Extreme SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2798
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (2), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Extreme SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is an Extreme SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Extreme SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Extreme SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Extreme isolated means that there's no Extreme SuperHyperEdge has it as an Extreme endpoint. Thus the Extreme SuperHyperVertex, V_3 , is excluded in every given Extreme SuperHyperConnected. 2807
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (3), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2815
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 3z.$$

- On the Figure (4), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2818
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$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} = \{E_1, E_2, E_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = z^3.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} = \{V_1, V_4\}.$$

$$\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} = 15z^2.$$

- On the Figure (5), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2821
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (6), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2824
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (7), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2827
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{12}, E_{13}, E_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (8), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2830
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (9), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2833
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+1}_{i=0}^9\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+1}_{i=11}^9, V_{22}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 20z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (10), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely 2836
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straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{12}, V_{13}, V_{14}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 4 \times 4z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (11), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_1, E_6, E_7, E_8\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2z^4. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (12), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_1, E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 5z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_{i=1}^{i \neq 4,5,6}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^5.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (13), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_9, E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_5\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3z^2.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (14), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (15), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward.

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_3, V_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (16), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2854
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^3.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (17), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2857
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (18), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2860
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2, E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^3. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1, V_2, V_6, V_{17}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 2 \times 4 \times 3z^4.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (19), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2863
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_{i+2_{i=011}}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 11z^{10}.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (20), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2866
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (21), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2869
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_2\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_1\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 10z.\end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (22), the Extreme SuperHyperNotion, namely, Extreme SuperHyperConnected, is up. The Extreme Algorithm is Extremely straightforward. 2872
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{E_3, E_4\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^2. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \{V_3, V_{10}, V_6\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= 3 \times 6z^3.\end{aligned}$$

The previous Extreme approach apply on the upcoming Extreme results on Extreme SuperHyperClasses. 2875
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Proposition 16.4. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. Then 2877
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$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} &= \\ &= \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{\text{Extreme R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} &= \\ &= \prod |V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 2}\end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let 2879

$$\begin{aligned}P : \\ V_2^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_2, \\ V_3^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, E_3, \\ \dots, \\ E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}, V^{\text{EXTERNAL}}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{\text{Extreme Cardinality}} - 1}.\end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 2880
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$$\begin{aligned}V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \sim V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{\text{EXTERNAL}}, V_j^{\text{EXTERNAL}}\} \subseteq E_z.\end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.5. In the Figure (23), the connected Extreme SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (23), is the SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.6. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} = \\ & = \{E_i\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = (|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1) \\ & \quad z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ & = \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}\}_{i=1}^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = \prod |V^{EXTERNAL}_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} z^{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 2} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & P : \\ & V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2, \\ & V_3^{EXTERNAL}, E_3, \\ & \dots, \\ & E_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1}, V^{EXTERNAL}_{|E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} & V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ & \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.7. In the Figure (24), the connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (24), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.8. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ SuperHyperConnected} = \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ & = |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}|_{Extrem\ e\ Cardinality} z. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-SuperHyperConnected} = \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extrem\ e\ R-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} = z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.9. In the Figure (25), the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (25), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.10. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ &\quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \underset{z}{\min} |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &\text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ &\mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only two SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.11. In the Extreme Figure (26), the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Extreme Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (26), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.12. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{E_a \in E_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}}, \\ & \quad \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| = \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ Quasi-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= z_{\min |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} \\ & \text{where } \forall P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}, |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \\ &= \min_i |P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)} \in P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected}} \\ &= \{V_a^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, V_b^{EXTERNAL} \in V_{P_j^{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}}, i \neq j\}. \\ & \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme \text{ V-SuperHyperConnected SuperHyperPolynomial}} \\ &= \sum_{|V_{ESHG:(V,E)}^{EXTERNAL}|_{Extreme \text{ Cardinality}}} = \left(\sum_{i=|P^{ESHG:(V,E)}|} (|P_i^{ESHG:(V,E)}| \text{ choose } 2) \right) = z^2. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there's no at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi may be up but the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. There are only z' SuperHyperParts. Thus every SuperHyperPart could have one SuperHyperVertex as the representative in the

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. Thus only some SuperHyperVertices and only minimum-Extreme-of-SuperHyperPart SuperHyperEdges are attained in any solution

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ V_2^{EXTERNAL}, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

is a longest path taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. The latter is straightforward. □

Example 16.13. In the Figure (27), the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, is highlighted and Extreme featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Extreme result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (27), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

Proposition 16.14. Assume a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected} &= \{E_i \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} \\ &= |i \mid E_i \in |E_{ESHG:(V,E)}^*|_{Extreme\ Cardinality}|z. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected} &= \{CENTER \in V_{ESHG:(V,E)}\}. \\ \mathcal{C}(NSHG)_{Extreme\ V-SuperHyperConnected\ SuperHyperPolynomial} &= z. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V^{EXTERNAL}_i, E^*_i, CENTER, E_j.$$

is a longest SuperHyperConnected taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} &\sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, & \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of SuperHyperConnected. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one SuperHyperConnected. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on SuperHyperConnected could be applied. The unique embedded SuperHyperConnected proposes some longest SuperHyperConnected excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Example 16.15. In the Extreme Figure (28), the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $NSHW : (V, E)$, is Extreme highlighted and featured. The obtained Extreme SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous result, of the Extreme SuperHyperVertices of the connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$, in the Extreme SuperHyperModel (28), is the Extreme SuperHyperConnected.

17 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)” with ISO abbreviation “J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res” in volume 1 and issue 1 with pages 06-14. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)” with ISO abbreviation “J Math Techniques Comput Math” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

In some articles are titled “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs ” in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [104]** by Henry Garrett

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Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [135]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 3230 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs” and published by Ohio: E-publishing: Educational Publisher 1091 West 1st Ave Grandview Heights, Ohio 43212 United State. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [136]** by Henry Garrett (2022) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 4117 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “Neutrosophic Duality” and published by Florida: GLOBAL KNOWLEDGE - Publishing House 848 Brickell Ave Ste 950 Miami, Florida 33131 United States. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s

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See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the 3115
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